

Assessment of Color Changes on Composite Resins, GIC and Tooth Under the Influence of CHX, CHX with ADS, Octinidine and Oil Pulling Mouth Rinses: An In Vitro Study

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Abstract

Background - Restorative dentistry has seen remarkable progress due to advancements in dental materials. The field is benefiting from the development of materials that offer improved aesthetics, durability, and bio-compatibility. Innovations such as resin based composites, ceramic materials, and bio-active substances are not only enhancing the functionality of restorations but also contributing to minimally invasive procedures and longer lasting results.

Aim - The aim of this study was to evaluate and compare the effect of various mouth rinses on Composite resin, GIC and natural teeth using UV Spectrophotometer: An in vitro study.

Material and Method - A total of 36 composite specimens comprising nanohybrid composite disks of size 10-mm diameter and 0.5-mm thickness were prepared on a customized model for standardization using the composite filling instrument. The specimens were cured with light curing unit for 20 s and polished with a composite polishing kit and a total of 36 GIC specimens comprising zirconomer disks of size 10-mm diameter and 0.5-mm thickness were prepared on a customized model for standardization using the GDC filling instrument. A total of 36 extracted human premolar teeth for periodontal and orthodontic purposes were selected for the study. Four mouthrinses comprising CHX and CHX with ADS, orahe pro and oil pulling were used. Baseline color values of natural tooth, composite resins and GIC were recorded using an ultraviolet spectrophotometer. After baseline spectrophotometric measurements, all the samples were subjected to the mouth rinses. The post immersion color values of the samples were then recorded, respectively, using the same spectrophotometer.

Statistical Analysis :- The statistical analysis was done using One way ANOVA and paired t-test.

Results :- Reflectance values showed a statistically significant difference between CHX, CHX with ADS, Orahe pro and Oil pulling among Composite resin, GIC, natural teeth.

Conclusion:- Within the limitations of the current study, CHX with ADS and Orahe pro may aid in avoiding stains, thereby making it more acceptable for patients.

Introduction

Restorative dentistry has seen remarkable progress due to advancements in dental materials. The field is benefiting from the development of materials that offer improved aesthetics, durability, and bio-compatibility. Innovations such as resin based composites, ceramic materials, and bioactive substances are not only enhancing the functionality of restorations but also contributing to minimally invasive procedures and longer lasting results¹.

Over the years, patient demand for natural looking restorations has driven the increased use of resin composites in restorative dentistry².

Composite resin has become a corner-

stone in restorative dentistry for both anterior and posterior teeth due to several reasons like enhanced physical properties, adhesive properties, versatility and minimally invasive property. Composite resins are highly valued for their ability to replicate the natural color and shade of teeth, making them the material of choice for esthetically pleasing dental restorations. This capability is attributed to several key factors like shade matching system, translucency, opalescence, customizable aesthetics and stain resistance. This aesthetic versatility has revolutionized the

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approach to restorative dentistry, allowing for functional repairs that are virtually indistinguishable from natural teeth³.

Nanohybrid composites have become a preferred choice in restorative dentistry consisting of milled glass fillers that acts as dispersed phase which provides better mechanical strength and surface finish as compared to hybrid composites³.

Zirconia reinforced glass ionomer cement (Zr-GIC) restorations have demonstrated significantly higher strength compared to conventional and silver reinforced GICs, particularly when used in stress bearing areas. This improvement is attributed to Zirconia's exceptional mechanical properties, which enhance the overall durability and fracture resistance of the cement.

Additionally, Zirconia reinforced GICs maintain better esthetics compared to silver reinforced counterparts, making them a preferred choice for visible restorations that require both strength and visual appeal. Unlike other additives, Zirconia does not dissolve with prolonged soaking time, ensuring the integrity and longevity of the material.

Despite Zirconia based GIC'S growing popularity, tooth-colored restorations are prone to discoloration, particularly from the consumption of colored beverages or the use of mouth washes¹².

Among the available mouthwashes, chlorhexidine gluconate a cationic chlorophenyl bisbiguanide with excellent bacteriostatic properties has proven highly effective in reducing dental plaque. Over the years, various formulations of chlorhexidine, including gels, chips, sprays, and mouthwashes, have been developed, with mouthwashes being the most commonly used. In many studies, chlorhexidine serves as a positive control to assess the efficacy of other products, as it is considered the gold standard. However, side effects such as undesirable tooth discoloration, an unpleasant taste, dryness, and a burning sensation in the mouth often discourage patients from using this mouthwash¹⁵.

To address the tooth-staining drawback of chlorhexidine (CHX), a CHX formulation with an anti-discoloration system (ADS) was introduced to the market. This innovative mouthrinse combines CHX with ADS to effectively prevent plaque formation while minimizing tooth staining. A key component of this formulation is Plasdone K-29/32, a water-soluble, high molecular weight homopolymer of vinylpyrrolidone, specifically designed as an anti-discoloration agent to reduce staining¹.

Octinidine Dihydrochloride (OCT) is a bispyridine derivative, chemically defined as N,N-[1,10-decanediyl-di-1(4H)-pyridinyl-4-pyridene] bis(1-octanamine) Dihydrochloride. This novel bipyridine antimicrobial compound has been developed as a potential antimicrobial and antiplaque agent for use in mouthwash formulations. Existing data suggest that a 0.1% OCT mouthrinse may offer significant clinical benefits in reducing plaque accumulation and gingivitis. Several studies have reported that OCT in mouth rinse form effectively inhibits dental plaque and caries in both rats and humans. Additionally, OCT has

demonstrated superior prolonged bacterial anti-adhesive activity compared to chlorhexidine¹⁷.

Oil pulling is a traditional Ayurvedic practice originating in ancient India, aimed at maintaining oral health. It is believed to treat over thirty systemic diseases while also offering numerous oral health benefits, including improved gingival health with reduced inflammation and bleeding, relief from symptoms of dry mouth, throat, and chapped lips, whiter teeth, reduced halitosis, enhanced oral hygiene, and the strengthening of muscles and jaws in the oral cavity¹⁸.

Since the color stability of composite and GIC still remains a long term clinical problem, this study was carried out to assess the color changes in teeth, composite resins and GIC under the influence of CHX with and without ADS, Octinidine and oil pulling mouth rinses using a spectrophotometer.

Material and Methods

A total no. of 36 nanoceramic composite samples was prepared. It was comprised 36 each Neospectra ST (Dentsply Sirona) disks of size 10mm and 1mm thickness. Samples were prepared on customized model for standardization using composite filling instruments (GDC). The thickness was confirmed by vernier caliper. The samples were cured with light curing unit (Ivoclar Vivadent) for 20 seconds and polished with composite polishing kit (Shofu).

A total no. 36 GIC samples were prepared. It was comprised 36 Zirconomer (Shofu) disks of size 10mm and 0.5mm thickness. Samples were prepared on customized model for standardization using filling instruments (GDC). The thickness was confirmed by vernier caliper.

36 freshly extracted mandibular premolars teeth for periodontal and orthodontic purposes was collected. Collected teeth were stored, sterilized and handled according to the occupational safety and health administration and the centre of disease control and prevention guidelines¹. OSHA enforces regulations to protect workers from physical hazards, such as falls, machinery accidents, chemical exposure, and other workplace dangers.

The samples which were prepared were immersed in distilled water in separate containers and incubated it at 37°C for 24 hours. After 24 hours baseline color values of each sample were recorded at 400nm and 700nm by using UV Spectrophotometer.

After baseline color measurement the sample were exposed to respective mouthrinses. Chlorhexidine (Hexidine), Chlorhexidine with ADS (Dr. Reddy's), ORAHX PRO (ABOTT), Pulling oil (DABUR) was used in this study.

Samples were divided into 3 groups for this study. Group 1 (n=36) Nanoceramic composite disks, Group 2 (n=36) Zirconia based GIC, Group 3 (n=36) Natural tooth. Further, each group was divided into 4 sub groups, namely A, B, C and D containing 9 samples each.

Samples under subgroup A from each group were subjected into chlorhexidine, samples under subgroup B from each group were subjected into chlorhexidine with ADS, samples under

subgroup C from each group were subjected into ORAHX PRO and samples under subgroup D from each group were subjected into pulling oil mouth rinse. Samples from each group were immersed in mouth rinses respectively for 1 minute twice daily till 21 days.

Between the exposure to the mouth rinse, sample were stored in artificial saliva at 37°C. Storage media were changed after every exposure of the sample to the mouth rinse.

Post immersion color values of the sample were recorded respectively by using same UV Spectrophotometer at 400nm and 700nm.

Result

Mean reflectance in Group 1: Subgroup 1 ≈ Subgroup 2 ≈ Subgroup 3 ≈ Subgroup 4

In Group 1, the mean reflectance value using 400 nm wavelength after completing the procedure (i.e., after 21 days) for Subgroup 1 was 1.77±0.11, for Subgroup 2 was 2.57±0.23, for Subgroup 3 was 2.15±0.10, and for Subgroup 4 was 1.31±0.11. There was a significant difference in the reflectance value between the groups, with F value 119.49 and p value 0.001.

In Group 1, the mean reflectance value using 700 nm wavelength after completing the procedure (i.e., after 21 days) for Subgroup 1 was 1.74±0.12, for Subgroup 2 was 2.45±0.16, for Subgroup 3 was 2.32±0.13, and for Subgroup 4 was 1.45±0.10. There was a significant difference in the reflectance value between the groups with an F value of 95.90 and a p value of 0.001.

Mean reflectance in Group 2: Subgroup 1 ≈ Subgroup 2 ≈ Subgroup 3 ≈ Subgroup 4

In Group 2, the mean reflectance value using a 400 nm wavelength after completing the procedure (i.e., after 21 days) for Subgroup 1 was 1.15±0.25, for Subgroup 2 was 1.34±0.25, for Subgroup 3 was 1.30±0.12, and for Subgroup 4 was 0.84±0.27. There was a significant difference in the reflectance values between the groups, with F value 7.17 and p value 0.001.

In Group 2, the mean reflectance value at 700 nm after completing the procedure (i.e., after 21 days) for Subgroup 1 was 0.90±0.24, Subgroup 2 was 1.58±0.07, Subgroup 3 was 1.22±0.13 and Subgroup 4 was 0.67±0.35. There was a significant difference in the reflectance value between the groups with an F value of 27.28 and a p value of 0.001.

Mean reflectance in Group 3: Subgroup 1 ≈ Subgroup 2 ≈ Subgroup 3 ≈ Subgroup 4

In Group 3, the mean reflectance value using 400 nm wavelength after completing the procedure (i.e., after 21 days) for Subgroup 1 was 1.73±0.14, for Subgroup 2 was 2.62±0.34, for Subgroup 3 was 2.35±0.13, and for Subgroup 4 was 1.21±0.14. There was a significant difference in the reflectance value between the groups, with an F value of 81.19 and a p value of 0.001.

In Group 3, the mean reflectance value using 700 nm wavelength after completing the procedure (i.e. after 21 days) for Subgroup 1 was 1.75±0.11, for Subgroup 2 was 2.45±0.30, for

Subgroup 3 was 2.27±0.18 and for subgroup 4 was 1.25±0.08. There was a significant difference in reflectance values between the groups with an F value of 71.64 and a p value of 0.001.

Mean reflectance of sub groups in all groups was: Subgroup 4 < Subgroup 1 < Subgroup 3 < Subgroup 2.

Discussion

Esthetics and appearance play a crucial role in modern dentistry. With the growing emphasis on smile enhancement, patients seek treatments that not only restore function but also improve their overall appearance. An ideal restorative material should closely mimic the natural characteristics of teeth in terms of shade, translucency, and surface texture while maintaining color stability over time. Materials such as composite resins, ceramics, and Zirconia have been widely used in modern dentistry due to their excellent esthetic and functional properties⁶.

Evaluating whether a restorative material truly mimics natural teeth is a complex task because multiple optical properties like reflectance, translucency, and transparency interact to create a lifelike appearance¹⁹.

Mouthwashes are medicated solutions formulated for gargling and rinsing to maintain oral hygiene and provide therapeutic benefits⁸. Mouth rinses are commonly used formulations for oral cleansing, especially before dental surgical procedures, as they help reduce microbial load in the oral cavity²⁰. However they are known to cause discoloration of teeth and restorations.

In this study we have evaluated the color changes on restorations and natural teeth after exposure to the mouthwashes. Color changes in materials can be evaluated using various instruments, such as spectrophotometers and colorimeters, which provide precise and objective measurements of color stability²¹. In this study, a spectrophotometer was used as it is considered more accurate for measuring color changes¹.

Group I

Composite resins have gained widespread popularity in restorative dentistry due to their superior esthetics, cost-effectiveness, and minimally invasive application. Their ability to closely mimic natural tooth structure makes them a preferred material for both anterior and posterior restorations⁷.

The clinical performance of dental resin composites has seen remarkable improvements, largely due to the incorporation of nano-fillers. These advancements have enhanced strength, wear resistance, translucency, and overall longevity, making modern composites more reliable and esthetically pleasing. The incorporation of well dispersed inorganic particles into the resin matrix plays a crucial role in enhancing the mechanical, esthetic, and functional properties of composite resins. These fillers improve the overall performance of polymer based restorations by increasing strength, wear resistance, and polishability while reducing polymerization shrinkage. The fillers in dental resins significantly influence their radiopacity, mechanical properties, wear resistance, and elastic modulus, making them a critical component in composite formulations. The type, size, shape, and

distribution of fillers determine how well a composite performs in clinical applications²². Previous studies have identified multiple chemical, physical, and environmental factors contributing to color changes in resin composites over time. These factors affect the resin matrix, filler properties, and overall composite stability, leading to discoloration²³.

Staining and discoloration are among the most common reasons for replacing tooth colored restorative materials, particularly composite resins. Discoloration can be classified into intrinsic and extrinsic causes, both of which affect the longevity and esthetic quality of restorations. Intrinsic discoloration can occur due to aging of material itself, like alteration of the resin matrix and changes in the interface of matrix and fillers. Extrinsic discoloration may occur due to adsorption or absorption of colorants from exogenous sources such as coffee, tea, nicotine, beverages, and mouthrinses⁹.

Staining susceptibility of resin composites is closely related to water sorption and hydrophilicity of the matrix resin. The ability of a composite to absorb water also makes it prone to absorbing stain inducing substances like tea, coffee, red wine, and dyes (e.g., Methylene blue). The glass filler particles will not absorb water in the bulk of the material, but, they can absorb water onto the surface. Extra water sorption may decrease the life of the resin composites by expanding and plasticizing the resin component, hydrolyzing the silane and leading to microcrack formation. As a consequence of the high water sorption and solubility of restorative resins, studies have shown that composite restorations may have decreased mechanical properties and reduced longevity.

The composition of the resin matrix plays a crucial role in determining the water sorption, solubility, hydrophilicity, and microstructure of composite resins, all of which directly impact their long-term color stability. Composites primarily composed of bisphenolA glycidyl methacrylate (Bis-GMA) oligomers tend to exhibit greater hydrophilicity and water sorption compared to those predominantly containing urethane dimethacrylate (UDMA). The incorporation of a small amount of triethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEGDMA) into a Bis-GMA based resin matrix can significantly enhance the composite's water sorption. This effect arises from the central repeating ethoxy group in TEGDMA, which has a strong affinity for water molecules through hydrogen bonding with oxygen, thereby increasing the surface hydrophilicity of the composite material. Composite resins with elevated water sorption and hydrophilicity are more prone to discoloration, as water absorbed colorants may penetrate the resin matrix. Additionally, the inorganic fillers in composite materials are believed to influence color stability, as their size, type, distribution, and interaction with the resin matrix can affect the adsorption and absorption of colorants.

The adhesion of external colorants to the surface and their penetration into the resin matrix can lead to color changes, ultimately affecting the esthetic quality of the restoration. Surface roughening caused by wear and chemical degradation can affect

gloss levels, making the composite more prone to extrinsic staining. In composite resins, insufficient curing and residual unconverted camphorquinone are key factors contributing to discoloration. Nanohybrid composites typically contain milled glass fillers (40 to 50 nm) as the dispersed phase, offering enhanced mechanical strength and a superior surface finish compared to hybrid composites³.

Resin composites with smaller filler particles, such as nano-hybrid and Nanofilled composites, are generally believed to offer a superior surface finish and gloss, which may contribute to improved color stability over time²⁶.

Group II

Glass Ionomer Cements (GICs), developed by Wilson and Kent, and are now widely used in clinical dentistry²⁷.

Glass Ionomer Cement (GIC) is a versatile dental material composed of fluoroaluminosilicate glass powder and polyacrylic acid, commonly used in various dental procedures due to its adhesion to tooth structure, fluoride release, and biocompatibility²⁸.

Over the past decade, glass ionomer powder has been reinforced with various nanoparticles, including amorphous materials like hydroxyapatite and metal nanoparticles, to enhance its mechanical properties, bioactivity, and antibacterial effects. A high-strength restorative material, reinforced with Zirconia fillers and known as Zirconomer (white amalgam), has recently emerged as an alternative to glass ionomer cement in dentistry. Zirconia (ZrO_2) is a white crystalline oxide of zirconium²⁹.

The composition of Zirconomer includes zirconium oxide, glass powder, tartaric acid, polyacrylic acid, and de ionized water as its liquid component (Silva et al., 2009). The primary component of Zirconia-reinforced GIC is nano-sized Zirconia filler particles, comprising 96.5% to 98.5% of the material. These filler particles are designed to enhance translucency, allowing for a closer resemblance to the natural tooth color³⁰.

The low pH of certain active preventive agents in mouthwashes can affect restorative resin materials by reducing hardness, increasing wear, and compromising color stability over time⁸.

Sub-group A

Chlorhexidine was first developed in the 1940s by Imperial Chemical Industries in England. Later, in 1954, Davis et al. conducted a study on polyguanides and discovered that certain bisbiguanides exhibited a broad antimicrobial spectrum³¹.

Chlorhexidine is a biguanide compound commonly prescribed by dentists for its strong bactericidal properties and effective anti-plaque action. It works by blocking free acid groups such as sulfates, carboxyl's, and phosphates, preventing bacterial adhesion and co-aggregation. Additionally, chlorhexidine interacts with negatively charged bacterial cell walls, disrupting their adhesion mechanisms. However, this compound is also associated with color instability due to its chromogenic potential, leading to brown staining on teeth, the tongue, and silicate or resin composite restorations. Various staining mechanisms have been

identified, including the degradation of chlorhexidine into parachloraniline, non-enzymatic browning reactions, protein Denaturation with metal sulfide formation, and the precipitation of anionic dietary chromogen by cationic antiseptics².

Chlorhexidine is widely regarded as the gold standard agent for chemical plaque control due to its proven clinical efficacy. It exhibits broad spectrum antibacterial activity while maintaining very low toxicity. Additionally, chlorhexidine has a strong affinity for epithelial tissues and mucous membranes, enhancing its effectiveness in oral hygiene applications. The use of chlorhexidine is associated with certain side effects that may impact patient compliance, with the most prominent being its tendency to cause staining³².

Sub-group B

To combat this disadvantage of chlorhexidine mouthwash, at the beginning of the 2000s in Italy, a patented system called ADS (anti discoloring system) was developed. The ADS system can disrupt the two primary reactions responsible for stain formation: the Maillard reaction and the protein Denaturation process. It aids in reducing the risk of side effects associated with the long-term use of alcohol-based mouthwashes, thereby enhancing patient compliance³³.

CHX with ADS contains the patented ingredient Plasdone K-29/32, a water-soluble, high molecular weight homopolymer of vinylpyrrolidone. It is specifically designed as an anti-discoloration agent, added to CHX to minimize staining. Plasdone K-29/32 functions by binding to stain-causing chemicals, enhancing their solubility, and facilitating stain removal. It is a non oxidative agent, as it is neither peroxide based nor a peroxide generator, and it is also nonabrasive¹.

Recent efforts to reduce these undesirable side effects have led to the addition of sodium metabisulfite and ascorbic acid to chlorhexidine. This combination, known as the Anti-Discoloration System (ADS), significantly minimizes adverse effects while maintaining the mouthwash's antiseptic efficacy³⁴.

Sub-group C

More recently, OctinidineDihydrochloride, a bispyridinamine, has gained attention as a promising alternative for use in oral antiseptics, offering properties comparable to those of chlorhexidine³⁵.

OctinidineDihydrochloride (OCT) is a novel antimicrobial cationic surfactant compound developed in the 1980s at the Sterling Winthrop Research Institute in Rensselaer, NY (Al-Doori et al., 2007; Slee & O'Connor, 1983)³⁶.

OctinidineDihydrochloride (OCT), a bispyridinamine, is a novel antiseptic agent developed in the 1980s. Since 1995, it has been licensed for use as an antiseptic in 20 European countries. Its molecular structure features two active cationic centers separated by a long aliphatic hydrocarbon chain, preventing interaction between them. This unique structure ensures toxicological safety, as it prevents the release of 4-chloraniline³⁷.

Studies have shown that OctinidineDihydrochloride (OCT) exhibits greater effectiveness than chlorhexidine in providing

prolonged bacterial anti-adhesive activity¹⁷.

Sub-group D

Oil pulling traces its origins back to ancient Hindu texts and scriptures. While alternative healing methods like oil pulling warrant further scientific exploration, limited studies have evaluated its oral health benefits. However, existing reports suggest that oil pulling can significantly enhance oral hygiene³⁸.

Dabur Red Pulling Oil Ayurvedic Mouthwash offers the benefits of Kavala Gandusha Therapy, an ancient Ayurvedic oral detox regimen. This oil-based mouth rinse involves swishing oil in the mouth, helping to protect against diseases of the mouth, teeth, and gums while providing numerous wellness benefits. It effectively kills 99.9% of germs and is enriched with natural oils like Coconut and Sesame, along with Ayurvedic herbs such as Tulsi, Clove, Cinnamon, and Thyme Mint. Developed by Dabur as a proprietary Ayurvedic formulation, it helps prevent gingivitis, plaque, bad breath, bleeding gums, swelling, and infections.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of this study, it can be concluded that composite resin, GIC, and natural tooth structures exhibit significant discoloration, when exposed to Chlorhexidine (Subgroup A) and oil pulling (Subgroup D) mouth rinses for a period of 21 days. To minimize staining associated with these rinses, it would be advisable to prescribe CHX with ADS (Subgroup B) and Orahex Pro (Subgroup C), enhancing patient acceptance and compliance as the sub-groups have not shown discoloration after exposure.

A final aspect of our study that limits its clinical relevance is the fact that in vivo conditions may be challenging due to inherent differences between laboratory settings and real-life oral environments.

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